
IMPORTANCE OF PLANTING VEGETABLE SEEDLINGS BY MACHINE

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Abstract.

In this article, the main essence of the mechanization of planting vegetable seedlings is that, taking into account the urgency of providing the population with vegetable products rich in vitamins of the future, it is necessary to plant vegetable seedlings on agricultural machines in a short period of time at low cost. and in quality planting, we will have other scientifically based information about the crop area, the demand for planted vegetable seedlings, planting periods and other agrotechnical requirements.

Key words.

Area, vegetable, seedling, machine, planting, methods, soil, row, depth, dust, soil moisture.

In the conditions of Uzbekistan, vegetable crops are harvested and cultivated. However, due to the lack of special seeders, the planting of vegetable seedlings is carried out many times through the field with foreign seeders that are not adapted to local conditions and artificial devices that are not scientifically based. This, in turn, leads to an increase in labor, working time, fuel consumption and other costs, and an increase in the cost of the product. In this regard, it is important to create and develop energy-resource-efficient aggregates that perform several actions during one passage of the aggregate through the field when planting vegetable seeds.

In the world, targeted scientific-research works are being carried out aimed at developing resource-efficient technologies and technical means for planting vegetable crops, ensuring resource efficiency in the working process of existing machines. In this direction, to develop a structure of a seeder that forms rows of seeds in the fields prepared for planting and plants vegetable seedlings on top of them, and to justify the parameters of its leveler and auger installed on the seedbed, which ensure that it works at the level of agrotechnical requirements in the processes of interaction with the soil. conducting targeted scientific research is considered one of the urgent issues [1-5].

The cultivated area for planting vegetable seedlings is plowed at a depth of 30-40 cm in November in the autumn season, and it is chiseled and ground twice in March. After that, egate is removed with the help of cultivators at an interval of 70 cm.

To prepare vegetable seedlings, vegetable seeds are sown in greenhouses at the end of winter and planted, and in the spring after the second half of March, depending on weather conditions, heat-loving plants such as cabbage, tomatoes, sweet peppers and eggplants are planted. 'chats are planted in open fields. 40-45-day-old kopchats of uniform size, dark green leaves, well-developed roots, not withered, not crushed, are selected for planting with the help of a machine. Cabbage kopchats should be 12-15 cm high (5-6 leaves), tomato kopchats 20-25 cm high (8-10 leaves).

Seedlings are placed in wide rows in rows with an interval of 60, 70, 80, 90 cm, or in a 50+90, 60+120 cm scheme in a belt-like manner, and are hung on tractors with up to 50 horsepower. it is sown using a threshing machine. If you hang a seedling machine on a 50-horsepower tractor, in the early spring, the cultivated fields may become denser and cause the soil structure to deteriorate. Planting process of SKN-6A seedling machine works on the basis of the following technological processes [6-10]. In this case, the seedling machine is planted under the control of 1 worker of the specified technological processes.

Schematic diagram of SKN-6A seedling planting machine.

1- base driving wheel; 2- koprik; 3 and 10- front and back seats; 4- onion; 5- cutting disc; 6 and 9 holders; 7,8 and 19- boxes with kopchat; 11- awning; 12-

compacting wheels; 13- irrigation pipe; 14- dosing device; 15th and 17th chain gears; 16th reducer; 18- finding pipe; 20- scaffolding; 21- tank.

It is required to prune the seedling in the machine in an upright position, without bending or damaging the roots. Kopchats without a lid are buried at a depth of 5-15 cm, with a lid at least 10 cm. The specified depth should be measured with an accuracy of ± 2 cm, the soil around the kopchat should be compacted. In irrigated agriculture, weeding is done simultaneously with planting [11-15].

Rows should be straight, deviation from the specified width should not exceed ± 2 cm (± 7 cm for adjacent rows). It is necessary to achieve 95% rooting of kopchat without a tube, and 100% of kopchat with a tube. The spacing of seedlings in crop rows can be up to 10-140 cm.

After planting seedlings, it is necessary to pay attention to soil moisture, watering if necessary. After 2-3 days, the plants are inspected and seedlings are planted in the wrong places. Cultivation is carried out between the rows at a depth of 15-16 cm, the surroundings of the plants are softened, they are fed with mineral fertilizers and watered.

In the next term, vegetable products in the areas where vegetable crops were planted early, and all agrotechnical measures during the growing season were carried out on time, will ripen early and be harvested. By preparing these areas for replanting in time, planting repeated vegetable crops in favorable periods, it is possible to achieve abundant harvest from them [16-21].

REFERENCES:

1. Закирова С.Х., Низомиддинова М.Ш., Мукимов З.А., Жалилов Э.К. Пески центральной Ферганы // Экономика и социум. 2021. №5-1 (84). URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/peski-tsentralnoy-fergany> (дата обращения: 30.03.2023).
2. X.A.Idrisov, Z.Mukimov va boshqalar. Results of Analytical Study of Growth, Development and Grain Yield of Mung Bean (*Phaseolus Aureus Piper*) Varieties. Turkiya. Vol.37, No.3, 2022. 8880-8886. 2022 y.
3. N.I.Teshaboyev, Mukimov Z., A.Iminchayev, Sh.Sh..Muhammadjonova. EFFECTS OF DEEP TILLAGE OF COTTON ROWS ON COTTON YIELD. 1 tom. 326-331 bet. Uzbekistan. 2021/6.
4. Mukimov, Zoxidjon Alijonovich. G'o'za qator oralariga birinchi ishlov berishda qatqaloqni yumshatishning ahamiyati // orienss. 2022. №10. Url:

<https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/g-o-za-qator-oralariga-birinchi-ishlov-berishda-qatqaloqni-yumshatishning-ahamiyati> (дата обращения: 30.03.2023).

5. Teshaboyev Nodirbek, Mamadaliyev Muhammadkarim, Muqimov Zohidjon. [Natural screen sanded sands field water capacity](#). №9.11 tom. ACADEMICIA: An International Multidisciplinary Research Journal. 1080-1082. South Asian Academic Research Journals, A Publication of CDL College of Education. 2021.

6. Sh.P. Saripov, Z.Mukimov. Kombinatsiyalashgan mashina takomillashtir-ilgan tekislagichi tuproq suruvchi plastinalarning harakat yo`nalishiga nisbatan o`rnatish burchagini aniqlash. Yuqori samarali qishloq xo`jalik mashinalarini yaratish va texnika vositalaridan foydalanish darajasini oshirishning innovatsion yechimlari. T 1. 164-168 b. Uzbekistan.

7. Sotvoldiev Nozimjon Zikiryaevich, Mukimov Zohijon Alizhanovich. [Selection And Justification of the Kinematic Scheme of the Grapple Mechanism of the Loader](#). Texas Journal of Multidisciplinary Studies Texas Journal of Multidisciplinary Studies. T 15. 59-63. 2022/12/14.

8. Mukimov Z. Yerlarni joriy sho`r yuvishga tayyorlash va o`tkazish. Ilmiy habarlar. Ilmiy habarlar. T 1. 1574. Uzbekistan. 2022/12.

9. Mukimov Z. Tok o`simligini kesishning o`ziga xos xususiyati. ILMIY XABARLAR. T 1. 1599. Uzbekistan.

10. Mukimov Z. Mevali ko`chatlarni ekish ishlariga tayyorlashning ahamiyati. ILMIY XABARLAR. T 1. 1643 s. Uzbekistan.

11. M.G`oziyev, Z.Mukimov va boshqalar. Bedani vilt inspeksiya va tuproqning biologik faolligi. AGROKIMYOHIMOYA VA O`SIMLIKLAR KARANTINI. T 1. Toshkent. 6-son. 28-29 b. Uzbekistan. 2022 y.

12. Маматожиёв Ш. И. и др. ФАКТОРЫ, ВЛИЯЮЩИЕ НА ПРОЦЕССЫ ХРАНЕНИЯ ЗЕРНА И НА ПОКАЗАТЕЛИ КАЧЕСТВА //Universum: технические науки. – 2020. – №. 12-4 (81). – С. 75-78.

13. Anvarjonovich D. Q., Ogli X. M. B. The effect of grain moisture on grain germination during grain storage //ACADEMICIA: An International Multidisciplinary Research Journal. – 2021. – T. 11. – №. 5. – С. 418-421.

14. Idrisov X., Matholiqov R., Xoliqov M. KUZGI BUG 'DOYDAN KEYIN EKILGAN MOSH NAVLARINING SIMBIOTIK FAOLIYATINI O`RGANISH //O'rta Osiyo ta'lim va innovatsiyalar jurnali. – 2022. – T. 1. – №. 2. – С. 51-56.

15. Маматожиев Ш. И. и др. ПРЕИМУЩЕСТВА НОВОЙ СИСТЕМЫ ПРИ ПРИЕМКЕ ЗЕРНА //Universum: технические науки. – 2020. – №. 12-2 (81). – С. 96-99.
16. Davronov Q. A., Xoliqov M. B. O. G. L. KUZGI BUG ‘DOY NAVLARINI SAQLASH DAVRIDA URUG ‘LIK NAMLIGINI UNUVCHANLIGIGA TA‘SIRINI O ‘RGANISH //Oriental renaissance: Innovative, educational, natural and social sciences. – 2022. – Т. 2. – №. 10. – С. 1318-1325.
17. Закирова С., Газиев М. Влияние применения органических и минеральных удобрений на агрохимические свойства спланированных бугристо-барханистых песков //Известия ВУЗов (Кыргызстан). – 2010. – №. 6. – С. 175-176.
18. Газиев М. А. и др. Экологические средства защиты хлопчатника от заболевания вилтом //Известия. – 2008. – Т. 1. – С. 84.
19. Turdaliyev A., Quldasheva M., Shoxobidinov A. QUMLI CHO ‘L TUPROQLARDA SHAMOL EROZIYASINI G ‘O ‘ZA HOSILDORLIGIGA TA‘SIRI //Science and innovation. – 2022. – Т. 1. – №. D8. – С. 189-197.
20. Mamatqulov O. O. O., Muqimov S. A. O. BATAT O‘SIMLIGI BIOLOGIYASI VA AGROTEKNIKASI //Oriental renaissance: Innovative, educational, natural and social sciences. – 2022. – Т. 2. – №. 10. – С. 1334-1340.
21. Sotvoldiev N., Mamatqulov O., Sodiqova Z. ИПАК ҚҰРТИ БОҚИШДА ИНФЕКЦИОН КАСАЛЛИКЛАРНИ ОЛДИНИ ОЛИШ ТАДБИРЛАРИ //Science and innovation. – 2022. – Т. 1. – №. D8. – С. 169-174.